

**FUNDAMENTALS AND MODELING PERSPECTIVES OF HUMAN PHYSIOLOGICAL
ADAPTATION TO EXTERNAL/INTERNAL SHIFTS**

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Abstract

The self-adjustment of human physiology to current external and internal physiochemical conditions is a well-known phenomenon. However, the observational data cover mainly surface manifestations while deep mechanisms are still unclear. In medicine, this knowledge gap often originates incorrect diagnoses and cure tactics. To fill this knowledge gap, it is necessary to form a concept capable of explaining the complex mechanism causally connecting environmental shifts with ultra-structural transformations at scales of cells and organs. The needed concept is based on five key theses: 1) every specialized cell has a basic program realizing the cell cycle; 2) its phases depend on cytoplasm's physiochemical parameters that are under external influences including those generated by other types of cells and induced an imbalance between rates of biosynthesis and molecular destructions; 3) the induced imbalance (II) impairs the normal metabolism accumulating in the cytoplasm interim products of two types (IP1s, and IP2s). IP1s penetrate the nucleus while IP2s go beyond impaired cells and circulate with body fluids; 4) IP1s, through modulating genes' expression, activate intracellular negative feedback mechanisms (INFMs); 5) under up to moderate II, INFMs minimize II while extreme chronic II can be minimized due to involvement of multicellular enhancers (MEs). They include both organs supplying impaired cells with materials and organs removing metabolic wastes. Activators of MEs are IP2s. The concept explains the principles of INFMs-MEs interaction and sheds new light on mechanisms bridging local intracellular adaptive rebuilding with known structural transformations at the scale of organs. Material flow alteration is necessary for the appearance and disappearance of organism scale internal driving forces of adaptive re-building. This concept is a basis for creating models that simulate important aspects of human integrative physiology.

Keywords: cell, energy, genes, cytoplasm, organs, interaction, evolution.

Highlights

- Cell is the lonely structural-functional unit providing reactive physiological adaptation (RFA)
- RFA starts when outer/inner factors impair metabolism accumulating adaptation factors (AFs)
- AFs control both genes expression in stagnated cells and state of organs that provide cell life
- RFA is a multiscale transitory processes providing synthesis on imposed rate of destructions
- Organs-scale adaptive alterations are consequences of stagnated cells' RFA and proliferation

1. Introduction

Humans and animals adapt to environmental changes using behavioral and physiological mecha-

nisms. Self-adjustment of human physiology to external and internal physicochemical changes is a well-known phenomenon. However, due to the complexity of the organism and methodological limitations, observational data mainly represent superficial manifestations, while the underlying mechanisms are still unclear. Moreover, traditional (standard) empirical studies of human adaptation to changed environmental factors are conducted within the framework of algorithms aimed at identifying and describing temporary changes in selected partial and very limited biometric indicators in response to the "immersion" of the organism in an environment with one (two, three) changed physicochemical factors. Figure 1 schematically presents typical empirical studies of the organism's adaptation to environmental changes and their main shortcomings.

Figure 1 A diagram illustrating standard empirical studies of human organism adaptation to environmental changes and its main shortcomings.

The researcher, carefully recording subsequent changes in the parameters of vital activity, publishes the materials as the final scientific result of the study. The maximum that is envisaged in such a study is a comparison of new data with data published by other researchers with similar observations, and a discussion of possible discrepancies, if any. In this way, the current database has accumulated and continues to expand. The approach has trained highly qualified specialists, but in narrow areas of adaptation biology (for example, on the problems of human adaptation to high [1] or low [2] temperatures, to high altitudes [3-7], to underwater depths [8], to high humidity [9] or dry air [10,11], to microgravity [12-14] to physical exertion [15], to psycho-emotional stress [16], etc.). The fundamental drawback of such approaches is that researchers operate with significantly limited biological entities, and many mechanisms and parameters involved in the actual provision of adaptive events are still unknown. At present, it is impossible to predict the trajectory of adaptation: too many random factors not taken into account in empirical research can cause almost kaleidoscopic changes in the picture of adaptation. Therefore, the existing database is insufficient to solve current problems of applied physiology and medicine. Specialists in these fields need a theory that can both explain patterns and trends and use it to build scenarios for managing adaptation trajectories.

One of the most fundamental questions here is how an urgent reaction to a change in environmental parameters differs from adaptation to new conditions. So far, the answers to this question concern mainly the temporary aspect of transient processes and do not reveal the deep essence of adaptation. Everything indicates that the basis of the relationship between the organism and the environment are mechanisms that prevent unacceptable, incompatible with life functional disorders. There are also hints that the deep cause of

such disorders is molecular destruction. But destruction is an integral part of life and accompanies it. A long-term balance between anabolism and catabolism is the key to stable life. In different phases of life, all three variants of inequality between these two phenomena can exist. This statement is true at all levels of organization – from cellular organelles, in cells, their colonies and organs, anatomical and functional systems and the organism as a whole. Therefore, it is important to understand the fundamental differences between the primary reaction of the organism to a change in the environment and the changes that gradually occur in the organism during long-term shifts in the environment.

Specialized receptors that react to specific physical and chemical changes in the external or internal environment are directly or indirectly connected with specialized neural structures that adaptively optimize the activity of certain physiological mechanisms of life support by changing the activity of specialized effectors. Consequently, at the first stage of response, the organism cannot know how long the new state of the environment will last. There are sufficient grounds for the assertion that evolutionarily accumulated mechanisms are sufficiently effective only for eliminating the consequences of short-term disturbances without structural reorganizations. As the duration of disturbance increases, certain unfavorable events must occur that worsen the quality of cell metabolism and life. It is precisely the nature of these events that empirical physiology has not yet revealed.

Over the last twenty years, the author's interests have focused on a different approach to this problem, as well as to the general problem of age-related deterioration of health due to a decrease in the effectiveness of self-regulation mechanisms. This approach was based on a rethinking of the emergence and evolution of two fundamental properties – homeostasis and adaptation [17].

An analysis of literature prompted us to see that early forms of these properties were emerged already in archaic unicellular ancestor organisms (UAO) that gave rise to multicellular organisms (MO). Mechanisms revealed as providers of MO's survival in unstable environmental conditions, already in UAOs include two sub-mechanisms: one provides cell energy balance, another – optimizes physiochemical parameters of the cytoplasm. Both mechanisms emerged as fighters with consequences of practically inevitable molecular destructions [18,19]. Human specialized cells continue to have those mechanisms appeared in ancestor UAOs but it is necessary to stress that in MO, the instability of local cellular environment is much more unpredictable. The single way the cell to be alive and well for a long time is to exclude chronic prevalence of the rate of macromolecules' decay over the rate of their synthesis.

Perhaps, the mitosis provided almost during the entire life span is one of the most often happening events altering the intracellular environment. The cell cycle is a complex event thoroughly organized by genetic mechanisms and depending on many factors [20-22]. Genetic mechanisms control both molecular synthesis and decay. On this background, a lot of factors, including those associated with the integrative physiology, can induce additional molecular destructions. Even under rest conditions, mechanisms providing functional integration of specialized cells indirectly cause molecular destructions. So, multicellularity exacerbated the need for compensatory synthesis of disintegrated molecules and increased the requirements for material and energy support of the biosynthesis [17].

The most particular homeostatic mechanisms that provide our relative independence from fluctuations in the living environment are also based on intracellular mechanisms accumulating ATP. Already understanding these fundamentals allowed us to look at individual adaptation as a specific kind of movement in a biological multi-parametric space. In this space, may be areas providing optimal-like physiology, and areas where intracellular destructions are critical for cells life. If so, the adaptation to the altered environment is a way to minimize these destructions. The adaptive movement must have at least one external initiator, one internal target-cell, and interim organs creating internal driving forces (IDFs) that transfer the local problem, born in the target-cell, to other cells of organism.

Adaptation is always structural even when adaptive re-structuring occurs in microscopic structures. Adaptation may either enlarge or decrease the biological structures. The speed of enlargement depends upon capability of cells to assimilate substrates. In case the summary needs in substrates exceed their current concentrations, special mechanisms must provide additional incomes of resources toward impaired cells. The speed of structural reductions mainly is determined by concentration gradients providing removal of excess molecules. So, at the organism scale, the re-configuring of material flows shapes the trajectory of adaptation in the parametric space. IDFs must be zero at the initial and final points.

In my opinion, this cardinally new view on adaptive re-arrangements deserves to be a subject for a proper scientific discussion.

The article, summarizing the author's ideas in this area, argues the general concept of organism's adaptation to altered physiochemical conditions of external and internal environments.

2. Conceptual notations

The needed concept cannot be based exclusively on empirics but requires alternative approaches capable to answer at least to following fundamental questions:

1. How many forms of adaptation exist?
2. Why the adaptation is necessary?
3. What will happen if the organism has no mechanisms for adapting its biochemistry and physiology to altered environment?
4. How the adaptation starts and when is complete?

Empiric research convincingly demonstrates that in the process of individual adaptation of the organism to changes in environmental conditions occurs in such macroscopic structures like organs and their anatomical-functional systems. Does it follow from these observations that each organ has special mechanisms that sense the need for adaptation and purposefully implement it? Although empiricists do not have any definitely answer to this non-trivial question they do not exclude such a possibility. What mechanisms coordinate adaptive changes in different organs? This is another fundamental question still without answer.

To answer these questions, it is necessary to first clearly establish the basic link in which the adaptation occurs. Our previous studies have shown that this link is a single cell (Grygoryan, 2004, 2024). The mechanism of spreading a local process on a larger scale is enigmatic.

Evolution has accumulated multiple mechanisms of cell adaptation to changes in the environment. Some of these mechanisms are passive, i.e. based on the initial redundancy of ways to provide a useful final effect. A good example is the adaptation of an aerobic cell to a lack of energy. There are anaerobic and aerobic pathways for the synthesis of ATP molecules. In addition, various carbohydrates, fatty acids, fats, and proteins are suitable as a substrate. Although the efficiency of ATP synthesis is not the same, the mechanisms function in parallel and the problem of cell survival is often solved automatically (without energy expenditure, by passive work of the chemical transformation chain). Against the background of passive adaptation, an aerobic cell has active mechanisms of adaptation to a continuing lack of energy by increasing the total surface area of the internal mitochondrial membranes. Adaptation is achieved both in a relatively fast way (by fusing individual, already existing mitochondria) and by their gradual proliferation. Another mechanism for increasing the rate of ATP synthesis is based on the non-uniform concentration of oxygen in the cytoplasm: mitochondria are sensitive to oxygen concentration gradients and move toward areas where this concentration is higher.

How to create an approach that can be both simple and productive enough for answering the upper formulated questions?

The approach we are searching for can be based on the fact that all our cells provide the basic functions already provided by UAOs. This means that despite specialization and specific functions at organs scales, our cells form a horizontal net in the frame of which

Figure 2 An original approach to study the organismic echo of cellular problems by means of a binary model (BM).

In BM, all cells of the organism are divided into two virtual cells: VC1 and VC2. VC1 represents a part of cells providing comfort metabolism. VC2 represents remained cells having impaired metabolism. Relative increase of active chemicals produced by VC2 elevates the level of organism's physiological activity (it can be measured using different variables).

VC1 represents the cells having normal (comfort, balanced) metabolism while VC2 represents the cells having metabolic problems appeared because of energy or material imbalances. VC2 cannot exist for a long time, so it seems reasonable to assume that there will be mechanisms minimizing the risk to be dead. As far as human cells cannot be in spore state, the single reasonable alternative one can imagine is to have special mechanisms coping with this dangerous state. Earlier it was hypothesized that VC2 are initiators of efforts aimed to elevate material inflows to enhance intracellular mechanisms providing biosynthetic transformations [23]. This hypothesis suggests that levels of organism's physiological activity (Basal, Moderate, or Extreme) indicate the number of problematic cells.

This approach opens novel opportunities to theoretically define the individual norm or assess the human physical health (HPH).

3. Information from cell physiology

Adult human organism consists of about 220 types of cells while the number of its cells is estimated approximately 40-60 of trillions. Dividing the last digit on the number of cell types shows that each cell type is represented in the body as a colony containing from several millions to billions of cells. Each colony is formed by mitosis, but the cells are not immortal, so the number of cells in any colony is dynamic. In addition, the cells of the same colony are not absolutely identical. The physicochemical characteristics of the environment where the cell is spatially localized undergo random or regular changes. This leads to the fact that new cells that appear at different times will have slight differences from other cells. Such differences lead to the fact that even with simultaneous stimulation of all the

they are competing for common resources. The assimilation rate is uncial for every cell. So, those cells currently having greater assimilation rate have more chances to provide normal metabolism than the cells possessing lower assimilation rate. Ignoring the quantitative aspect of this diversity, we can qualitatively divide all cells to two virtual cells – VC1, and VC2 (see Fig.2).

cells of the colony, their reaction can have asynchrony. In fact, such asynchrony determines the nonlinear input-output relations of the entire colony. Considering that each organ contains several colonies of different specializations, the reason for the nonlinear input-output relations of the entire organ becomes clear. The mentioned features of colony dynamics already predetermine the non-stationarity of the function of every organ. Ignorance or failure to consider this circumstance will give rise to incorrect conclusions regarding the causes of functional shifts in the body.

Mitosis is one of basic events manifold provided by the most of specialized cells. The quality of mitosis is crucial therefore multiple evolutionarily chosen check-point mechanisms exclude wrong interim transformations happening with casual intensity [20-22]. The high sensitivity of tertiary and quaternary structures of biological macromolecules to the physiochemical alterations in cytoplasm forces the cell to repeatedly re-synthesize structural components needed to create a daughter cell. This randomly increases expenditures of ATP molecules and lengthens the duration of different phases of the cell cycle. Both events affect the cell physiology and, depending on number of affected cell may modify organs' and integrative physiology.

Taking into account nuances mentioned above let's analyze differences of adaptation to increased or decreased molecular destructions.

4. Adaptation to increased destructions

Scenarios of adaptation to increased molecular destruction may differ depending on their dynamics and scales. Before considering typical adaptation scenarios for local, regional, and global (organism-scale) increased molecular destructions, it is useful to consider some specific aspects of nuclear control of metabolism.

The nuclear control of cell life is indisputable. Many exact mechanisms of this control are still very approximately. However, general control of interactions between specialized sites of DNA and transformations in cytoplasm are almost clear. Expression of

certain genes determines the current due rate of biosynthesis. In case this event goes wrong, the transformation

origins interim products of two types – IP1s and IP2s (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 A picture schematically illustrating interactions between the cell nucleus and cytoplasm.

Special sites of DNA through the expression of genes set the required metabolic rate. If any biochemical transformation is interrupted at intermediate stages, chemical substances that act as agents of a problem begin to accumulate. Some of these agents (IP1s), penetrating the cell nucleus, increase the expression of those genes that activate the synthesis of substances, the deficiency of which interrupts this metabolic chain. The appropriate regulator (intracellular negative feedback mechanism) aims to eliminate metabolic problems and restore the balance between the rates of synthesis and decay of cellular structures or consumables (for example, ATP). Another group of intermediate agents (IP2s) enters the intercellular space. Some of these agents influence local target cells, and others, circulating with lymph and blood, can reach remote target cells associated with life-support organs. Thus, in multiple ways (local vasodilation, increasing the function of the cardiac pump, external respiration, the erythropoiesis system), a reliable compensation for metabolic imbalance is achieved precisely in those cells where it arose.

According to Fig.3, every cell possesses multiple opportunities for reliable compensation for the metabolic imbalance that appeared because cytoplasmic factors increased the rate of molecular destruction. Depending on cell type and phases of the cell cycle, DNA sets the due metabolism rate. Ideally, the cell being in the G0-G1 phase does provide a balance between biosynthesis and destructions while in phases of S, G2, or M, the rate of biosynthesis exceeds the destructions' rate. However, different invasions can increase the rate of destruction causing imbalances. In such scenarios, some metabolic chains cannot be completely provided. So, every disrupted metabolic transformation leads to the accumulation in the cytoplasm of certain interim products. Among them, two groups – IP1s, and IP2s, are principal for understanding how cells fight metabolic imbalances.

Representatives of IP1s, penetrating the cell nucleus, increase the expression of those genes that activate the synthesis of substances, the deficiency of which interrupts this metabolic chain. The appropriate regulator (based on intracellular negative feedback mechanisms – INFMs) aims to eliminate metabolic problems and restore the balance between the rates of synthesis and decay of cellular structures or consumables (for example, ATP). However, the compensatory power of INFMs is limited by current cytoplasm concentrations of scours building materials and ATP. Therefore, extreme imbalances require additional mechanisms to provide adequate intracellular physiochemical conditions. This function is associated with IP2s that enter the intercellular space. Some of these agents influence local target cells, and others, circulating with lymph and blood, can reach remote target cells associated with life-support organs. Thus, in multiple ways (local vasodilation, increasing the function of the cardiac pump, external respiration, the erythropoiesis system, as well as activating organs removing metabolic wastes), A reliable compensation for metabolic imbalance can be achieved precisely in those cells where it arose when a functional super-system (FS), providing cells' life is properly tuned. FS functionally integrates INFMs with multicellular mechanisms generally enhancing INFMs. The multicellular mechanisms of FS include both local mechanisms (vasodilation and angiogenesis) and organism-scale mechanisms [23-26]. The latter includes the cardiopulmonary system, the system of erythropoiesis, the system of thermoregulation, the system of water-electrolytic balance (kidneys, skin, and lungs), and the digestive system with their neural-hormonal controllers.

Adaptation to the increased destructions in cells of a local area rarely needs multi-scale activities. Evolution saved local mechanisms capable increase inflows of materials (nutrients, water, oxygen) necessary for additional biosynthesis in relatively localized body ar-

cells without cardinal changes in the physiology of multicellular FS. Indeed, the local concentration of several representatives of IP2 lowering the tonus of arterioles causes vasodilatation and increases the blood flow to impaired cells. If the arterial blood contains the required concentrations of materials, it will provide additional synthesis of ATP using the existing mitochondria. In the scenario of short-term impairment, this response is enough to eliminate the problem. Under chronic local impairment, insertional mechanisms like mitochondrial movements toward cytoplasm sectors with higher oxygen concentration will be activated. If the impairment is not eliminated, mitochondrial proliferation slowly elevates the total mitochondrial surface until the problem is solved.

Adaptation to the increased destructions in cells of a regional area will start by analogy with the previous situation. Under large amounts of impaired cells, the regional vasodilatation can decrease the systemic arterial pressure. This lowers the flows affecting processes aimed at powered biosynthesis. Therefore, additional mechanisms do elevate the heart pump function with

parallel constriction of arterioles. Note, that in the impaired regions local vasodilators continue to provide a due radius of supply vessels.

According to Fig.4, the final result of organism-scale adaptation to energy shortage is arterial blood with elevated pressure, flow, and enriched chemistry. Due to vasodilation in zones of impaired cells, the main part of cardiac output (CO) is directed to these cells. The increase in CO is due to the heart rate (HR) and stroke volume (SV) elevation. However, HR's increase leads to a shortening of diastole, worsening cardiomyocytes' recovery. If the synthesis of ATP in cardiomyocytes is not properly increased, calcium ions accumulated in sarcoplasmic cisterns lower the contractility of cardiomyocytes generally decreasing SV and CO. Thus, the due level of CO required for impaired cells can be ensured through combining of two inertial mechanisms of adaptive re-structuring: 1) an enlargement of mitochondria in cardiomyocytes; 2) proliferation of cardiomyocytes. Both these re-arrangements accompanied by lower HR due to elevated activity of the parasympathetic nerve are well-known in athletes.

Figure 4 Schematic view on adaptive responses provided by different organs and anatomical-functional systems in case of global lack of energy caused by hypoxia and lowered glucose.

Note that even under such a global problem, some cells currently not consuming large amounts of ATP provide normal metabolism and do not produce IP2s. Producers of IP2s are the impaired cells. Theoretically, originators of massive impairments may not be exclusively hypoxia and lowered glucose: other environmental shifts also may have such physiological effects. It is important to note that 9 independent ways illustrated here can completely adapt the organism to the altered environment if only the digestive system provides the needed resources.

Adaptation to organism-scale worsening of cells metabolism includes the considered conservative scenarios including also additional tactics too. The figure

illustrates how the impaired cells do produce IP2s generally creating arterial flow with enriched substrates and under elevated pressure enough to provide all impaired cells with ATP and building materials.

Usually, environmental alterations are dynamic. To briefly consider the dynamics of cardiomyocytes' adaptation, instead of an abstract cardiomyocyte it is necessary to analyze a colony of cardiomyocytes. As every cell colony normally is built of non-homogenous cells of the same specialization, for every time moment the colony contains cells of different functional states. Some cells are well-powered while others are comparatively less-powered and need additional ATP and substrates to up-build their organelles. Such heterogeneity

suggests that under increasing environmental loads the less-powered cells are more vulnerable and represent the colony's weak chains that first will impair their metabolism. So, namely, these cells are the early producers of adaptation factors IP1s and IP2s. In case the environmental dangerous factors continue to rise, new cells having moderate power do feel metabolic problems. Under up-to-extreme enlargement of environmental negative factors, this scenario can cover the entire colony. There are reasons to call such adaptation an expanding adaptation. As every organ normally is built of several cell colonies (CCs), analogical dynamics may appear in other CCs too. Certainly, every CC can have specific dynamics thus the organ-scale dynamics hardly will be of simple shape. This conclusion applies to the adaptation trajectories appearing at the organism scale too.

The pattern of adaptation of the myocardial cell colony is applicable to all cell colonies, including receptor cells. Additionally, this aspect is considered in the discussion section.

5. Adaptation to decreased destructions

It is well-known that heart hypertrophy and vascular wall thickening are indicators of an organism's adaptation to physical exercise. This process is reversible – the adaptation to less physical activity gradually restores these cardiovascular parameters. Analogical reversibility is observed in other types of specific adaptation-dis-adaptation events too. As the proposed adaptation theory explains such structural alterations through intracellular re-arrangements, let's analyze the possible mechanisms of the organism's adaptation to the lowered rates of molecular destruction.

First, it is necessary to stress that the decreased molecular destructions are not dangerous and regularly take place. Certainly, the DNA, which is both the activator of biosynthesis and its suppressor, manifold combines these opportunities to regulate the cell cycle. In particular cases, often DNA inhibits certain chains of biosynthesis for returning the cell from the G₁ phase to the G₀ phase.

In the course of the article, the most interesting question is how the organism, already structurally adapted its certain organs to higher levels of biosynthesis, can feel the restored environmental conditions and start to destroy organs until recovering their initial sizes. In my opinion, the answer to this question hides in total competition between cells for common resources. Indeed, under conditions when the current concentration of resources is insufficient to meet the

needs of all pretends, only the cells with higher assimilation capacity can completely satisfy the "appetite". As already mentioned above, every colony contains some amount of cells that have different parameters including those determining the "appetite". Even the cell colony adapted to a higher destruction rate can include both mighty and weak cells. So, under lowering of destructions, the mighty cells lower their biosynthesis thus some amount of nutrients, water, and oxygen becomes accessible for relatively weak cells. The colony and the organ built of such colonies do produce their output function through activating of other combinations of cells. But this explanation cannot fully cover the mechanism of dis-adaptation. The matter is that during adaptation to elevated destructions, cells use two ways. One of them based on doing the cell more powered through up-building of its organelles was already considered. The second way is the proliferation of cells. Several agents from the IPs for example, the so-called hypoxia-inducible factors – HIFs) are activators of both erythropoiesis and proliferation of cells involved in chains of organs responsible for oxygen capture and transporting to consumers [27, 28]. Namely, organs' compensatory (adaptive) hypertrophy is mainly provided by cell proliferation.

6. Modeling Perspectives

To model the mechanisms of adaptation to environmental shifts, it was necessary to first create a basic complex model of the FS under physiological norm conditions. However, such models have not been proposed so far. The most complex model, proposed by Arthur Guyton and co-authors, described only the general regulation of blood circulation [29]. The need for complex models describing vital phenomena in the cell, organs, subsystems, up to integrative physiology, was recognized back in the late twentieth century and formalized as the concept of "Physiome" (<http://www.iups.org/physiome-project/>; <http://physiomeproject.org/about/molecules-to-humankind>; <https://www.auckland.ac.nz/en/abi/our-research/research-groups-themes/physiome-project.html>).

Despite the significant financial and intellectual resources involved, the concept of "Physiome" did not achieve its goals. In my opinion, one of the main reasons was the lack of understanding of the mechanisms of integration of different-scale biological processes [30]. The concept of adaptive response to changes in the external and internal environments proposed in this article is intended to fill precisely this theoretical gap. Figure 5 shows the block diagram of the required basic complex model.

Figure 5 A scheme of a complex mathematical model describing the interaction of basic mechanisms determining the dynamics of human body fluids.

The dynamics of four intercommunicating virtual compartments (cellular, intercellular, cardiovascular, and lymphatic) can be modulated by neural-hormonal mechanisms controlling the energy balance, and functions of the lungs, kidneys, thermoregulatory system and taking into account the food and water intakes.

The complex model functionally combines component models [31-37]. Already the simulations illustrated in these publications show that the basic complex model quite satisfactorily imitates the functioning of both the FS's components and its holistic response to test situations. This gives grounds to believe that with the proper refinement of the models and the inclusion of mechanisms for adaptive restructuring under limited resources, the advanced model and simulation technology can become an additional research tool. At this moment, my research team is focused on creating mathematical models and specialized computer simulators capable of realistically simulating both the function of organs and systems involved in FS and several aspects of FS's adaptive rearrangements under relatively short-lasting environmental disturbances.

7. Discussion

Conventionally, biologists use the term “functional adaptation” to denote adaptive responses, occurring urgently, and the term “structural adaptation” to denote adaptive effects developing slowly. In my opinion, this separation is not correct. Every so-called functional adaptation is provided by a control mechanism (CM) based on feedbacks. Such a mechanism usually includes a sensory link, afferent link, central link, efferent link, and effectors. Each link is a cell colony (CC) collected of common specialization dynamic cells that may have slight ultrastructural peculiarities modifying their functionality. As every specialized CC is also a dynamic object, the CM usually demonstrates temporal fluctuations. Perhaps, the energy aspect of such fluctuations needs to be some more thoroughly analyzed than it was done.

Normally, due to proper inflows, every cell is energetically well-balanced. However, under intensive long functioning, the cell meets energy problems that can be best illustrated using an abstract excitable cell like a neuron (see Fig.6 illustrating a stylized image of neuron's action potential (AP)).

Figure 6 The stylized image of an action potential (AP).

Resting potential (RP) at -70 mV is below the threshold (-55 mV). Local subthreshold stimuli also cause small local changes in the membrane potential. These local effects normally are rapidly damped. When the amplitude of the stepwise stimulus exceeds the threshold level, a huge number of the membrane ion channels become almost simultaneously quickly opened leading to the peak transmembrane potential of 40 mV. Crossing the zero line (overshoot) occurs because the ion motion is under the control of both electrical and concentration gradients. After transmembrane potential reaches the peak value, the phase of repolarization begins. But this inverse movement also passes the starting line of RP and eventually approaches the RP. It is crucial to accent: that the last phase of AP (see dotted circle) is not a passive process but requires some amount of ATP. Thus, each single neuron's AP diverts a certain part of the energy to recover its excitability.

According to Fig. 6, sub-threshold stimuli do not cause the breakdown of the membrane. But they open a few ion channels lowering the RP. In a real cell, such fluctuations of RP are frequent events. If the cell does not actively compensate for these effects RP eventually drops. In the normal neuron, the stability of RP is supported by the consumption of ATP at a rate proportional to the intensity of local fluctuations of RP. This is important for correct analysis of energy aspects of the long-term functioning of excitable cells. Events occurring during the first phase of the cell response to external stimuli are initiated by the energy of an external stimulus and then supported by transmembrane concentration and voltage gradients. The direction of these processes coincides with the direction of external driving force breaking the stable disequilibrium between the cytoplasm and extracellular fluid. Qualitatively different events underlie AP's second phase. The initial value of the transmembrane concentration gradient is so great that a neuron can consistently generate several thousands of impulses without a significant decrease in the initial amplitude of AP. The average duration of the impulse is about 2 ms. Without additional energy, an average neuron can respond to external stimuli in less than $2-3$ seconds. Therefore, for the full recovery of RP, the neuron is forced to spend a certain amount of ATP after each single AP. The same conclusion is true for other types of excitable cells. This is a very important detail of the excitation-recovery cyclic process which plays a determinant role in the reversible adaptation.

Certainly, the adaptation to environmental shifts suggests that the organism has both receptors directly or indirectly registering the shift and interim structures transmitting information to target cells located in other parts of the body. The presence of such mediators is already the first step in the integration of more than one group of cells into the adaptation process. The involvement of additional cells localized in different organs in this process is due to the integrative role of neural-humoral mechanisms of cell life support. I would like to emphasize that the FS named above arose precisely for cell life support, while all other effects are indirect manifestations of the functioning of this FS.

Since traditional animal and human physiologists continue to study fragments of the organism, integrative physiology is understood very superficially, and then mainly in terms of mechanisms for providing movements. In trying to build a theory of the adaptive response of the organism to exogenous and endogenous shifts, one is forced to fantasize. Fortunately, my professional activity is connected with mathematical modeling and computer simulations of life processes, which allows me to obtain additional information from the models.

The role of energy is so important for life that evolution has conserved many mechanisms to minimize the lack of ATP. Perhaps the fastest is the mechanism based on the feedback between the concentrations of AMP, ADP, and ATP, on the one hand, and the rate of mitochondrial synthesis of ATP molecules, on the other hand. Much of this rapid regulation is due to AMP-activated protein kinase [38-41]. Other mechanisms (movement of mitochondria, their fusion-division, proliferation), only emphasize the importance of energy in the life of cells. The volume of the article does not allow us to dwell on these mechanisms in detail. There is also no opportunity for a detailed analysis of the specific mechanisms that adapt cells to very specific conditions of their existence in various organs [42]. Only some of them will be described below to emphasize a new vision of their organismic role as mediators of cell adaptation.

Although the concept of adaptation proposed in the article as a way to combat the negative consequences of induced molecular destruction is logical, it is not obvious. This is partly because empirical physiological studies of regulatory mechanisms were limited to one or another anatomical and physiological system (cardiovascular, respiratory, water-electric, energy, immune, digestive, etc.). In such studies, the authors tried to determine the classical regulatory chain, including links of receptors, afferent, central, and efferent conduction pathways, and ending with the effector link. In cases of humoral regulators, it was often important not so much to establish the entire regulatory circuit but to identify the primary chemical agent sensitive to a specific biological parameter. Such preference had an applied focus since knowledge of the structure of this agent potentially opened the way to its artificial synthesis and use in the treatment of certain pathologies. Perhaps the most striking example of this type of research is angiotensin. It was originally discovered as an endogenous substance associated with another substance produced in the kidneys when blood pressure in the renal afferent arteries falls. For this reason, this substance was named renin. Research has established that renin molecules undergo successive biochemical changes in the liver, producing a substance (angiotensin-2) that has a pronounced vasoconstrictor effect. It is this circumstance that served as the basis for its name. A huge number of studies have been devoted to establishing the complex effects of angiotensin-2, as well as its versions known as angiotensins 1-7 [43-45]. In cardiology, agents that inhibit the activity of angiotensin-converting enzymes (ACE) are used to combat arterial hypertension (AH). It was later discovered that the kidneys

are not the only organ where renin is synthesized: under certain conditions, it is produced by the heart, liver, skeletal muscles, and also the brain [43,45]. To distinguish the effects of angiotensins associated with the kidneys or other renin producers, it is customary to designate them by different terms: the central renin-angiotensin system (cRAS) and the local renin-angiotensin system (lRAS) [43]. It would seem that this has clarified everything and that we can continue to establish the quantitative aspects of the functioning of these two mechanisms in the norm and the development of hypertension. But, especially taking into account the alternative pathophysiological mechanisms of hypertension [42], another aspect of the renin-angiotensin mechanism seems important to me.

Each cell of the body has a certain mechanism to combat the deterioration of its metabolism. The universal hypothetical diagram of this mechanism, based on IP1s and IP2s, was described above. In light of this hypothesis, it is easy to see that renin is one of the IP2s. Moreover, other known adaptation factors (VEGF, Hifs, NO, SO₂, CO, CO₂, etc.) should be attributed to the IP2s group. There is a possibility that this list will be expanded over time. I hope that this article will serve as a trigger signal not only for rethinking the functioning of the body as a community of dynamic and adaptive cells but will also encourage empirical biologists to develop experimental methods for searching for specific factors of adaptation. For my part, I note that this understanding of the body has already led to a rethinking of not only the level of the so-called normal blood pressure [32,46] but also the deep mechanisms that form the individually optimal parametric space of physical health and its dynamics [47,48].

The above arguments are based not only on the analysis of observational data from empirical biology but were also tested by us using mathematical modeling. Special models, created to simulate intracellular mechanisms working against energy shortage, described three mitochondrial mechanisms: movement toward higher cytoplasm oxygen concentration, a fusion of mitochondrion, and increasing the total surface of the cell's mitochondria through proliferation [49]. Simulations demonstrated the comparative effects of these adaptation ways for scenarios suggesting sufficient source materials for providing the needed ultrastructural up-building. The cell's model was incorporated into a model of the abstract cell population. This

research aimed to analyze the main effects, concerning individual differences of cells in an abstract colony.

Perhaps, one of the main simulation results was the internal causal connection between statistics of individual differences, on the one hand, and the shape of the trajectory presenting temporal dynamics of the colony's function, on the other hand. It simulated an input step action for the whole cell colony [32]. The total effect as a temporal sum of elementary output effects of cells depends on variations of individual thresholds. It was found that under a uniform distribution of the number of cells with given thresholds of response, the total production of cells increases linearly. With a bell-shaped symmetric distribution of the specified cellular heterogeneities of thresholds, the trajectory of the total production of cells has the form of a symmetric S-shaped curve. With asymmetric distributions of thresholds, the output curve is also asymmetric. This explains how biological nonlinearities met in a huge number of quantitative investigations are formed: their shape is a consequence of three fundamental features: 1) objects are built of multiple microscopic components of common architecture; 2) components may have slight heterogeneities modulating their behavior in the same environmental alteration; and 3) the object's total function is a temporal sum of components' dynamic responses [50].

Some words about the potential medical use of the FS-concept considered in the article. FS shapes the multi-parametric space (MPS) that medics use to evaluate and control HPH. However, no technology provides a correct assessment of HPH. At least three circumstances don't allow physicians to do this. First, no concept argues the complete list of parameters shaping MPS. Second, there is no diagnostic technology for simultaneously measuring the values of MPS's components at sub-cellular, cellular, colonial, organ, and organism scales. Third, the MPS always is individual. This systemic view on HPH suggests that the correct medical technology for assessing HPH must be based on deep mechanisms that determine the multiway dynamics of MPS fluctuating in shape without any serious pathology.

8. Conclusion

Graphically, the general theory of reversible adaptation is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Graphical presentation of the general theory of reversible adaptation.

The main statements of the theory can be formulated as follows:

1. The reversible physiological adaptation of a human organism (or other multicellular organism) to current living conditions is a transitory process (TP) occurring due to passive and reactive mechanisms.

2. The passive adaptation appears because the cell possesses multiple mechanisms each with specific efficiency leading to a useful output effect. Each mechanism is tuned for concentrations of specific physicochemical factors. An appearance or disappearance of the minimal concentration automatically switches on or off the mechanism altering the output effect.

3. The reactive adaptation (RA) appears because of induced changes in cell metabolism. RA can be of two scenarios: adaptation to elevated or lowered molecular destructions. Both scenarios develop in time lasting until the amount of cells with impaired metabolism is minimized. TP starts in cells where induced molecular destructions accumulated interim products (IPs) activating intracellular and multicellular negative feedback mechanisms commonly providing the cell energy balance.

4. Intracellular genetic mechanisms (IGMs) provide inverse proportionality between concentrations of particular IPs and expression of those genes controlling the total surface of inner membranes of mitochondria. The ultra-structural up-building in mitochondria is the main way to maintain the long-term energy balance at the forced rate of ATP consumption. Under essential and chronic energy imbalance in a large number of cells, accumulated special IPs penetrate intercellular space and activate multicellular mechanisms (MMs) that enhance the efforts of IGMs.

5. The altered functions of MMs re-configure blood flows and provide arterial blood with a higher concentration of materials necessary for intracellular up-building. Additionally, organs and systems purifying the cytoplasm in impaired cells are also activated

due to specific IPs. These organism-scale changes create the internal driving forces (IDFs) of adaptation. IDFs determine the adaptation trajectory thus parallel with the minimization of IPs, IDF also goes down.

6. The theory covers both adaptation to increased energy consumption and adaptation to external/internal environmental conditions that lower the energy consumption rate. In the last mode, the adaptation occurs due to a passive mechanism: the lowered rate of ATP consumption decreases concentrations of IPs lowering the activities of both IGM and MM.

7. The phenomenon of organ-scale restructuring is a passive consequence of specific IPs (Hifs, VEGFs, others) controlling the mechanisms of cell proliferation.

8. The proposed concept of an organism's physiological adaptation to external/internal challenges sheds new light on the mechanisms of essential arterial hypertension, considering it a way of compensating for the impairment of cell metabolism.

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